

Supplementary materials for

Quantifying the coupling effects of tectonics, climate, and lithology on the main drainage divide of a mountain belt

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Supplementary text

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SUPPLEMENTARY TEXT

Detailed derivation for the analytical solution to Equation (5) when $bm = 1$

Eq. 5 serves as the constraint equation governing the position of the steady-state

MDD within a mountain belt:

$$\frac{H_r}{H_p} = \frac{\int_0^{D_r - x'_{c(r)}} \frac{U_r + \frac{x'_r}{M}(U_p - U_r)}{K_r T_r^{bm-1} k_r^m (D_r - x'_r)^{bm} - V_r - \frac{x'_r}{M}(V_p - V_r)} dx'_r}{\int_0^{D_p - x'_{c(p)}} \frac{U_p - \frac{x'_p}{M}(U_p - U_r)}{K_p T_p^{bm-1} k_p^m (D_p - x'_p)^{bm} + V_p - \frac{x'_p}{M}(V_p - V_r)} dx'_p} \quad (5)$$

Divide Equation (5) through by U_p :

$$\frac{H_r}{H_p} = \frac{\int_0^{D_r - x'_{c(r)}} \frac{\frac{U_r}{U_p} + \frac{x'_r}{M} \left(1 - \frac{U_r}{U_p}\right)}{K_r T_r^{bm-1} k_r^m (D_r - x'_r)^{bm} - V_r - \frac{x'_r}{M}(V_p - V_r)} dx'_r}{\int_0^{D_p - x'_{c(p)}} \frac{1 - \frac{x'_p}{M} \left(1 - \frac{U_r}{U_p}\right)}{K_p T_p^{bm-1} k_p^m (D_p - x'_p)^{bm} + V_p - \frac{x'_p}{M}(V_p - V_r)} dx'_p}$$

Let $X = \frac{U_r}{U_p}$ and $Y = \frac{D_r}{M}$, it follows that $D_r = MY$ and $D_p = M(1 - Y)$. X and Y

represent the abscissa and ordinate of the curve in Figure 2, respectively. Substituting

these into the above equation yields:

$$\frac{H_r}{H_p} = \frac{\int_0^{D_r - x'_{c(r)}} \frac{X + \frac{x'_r}{M}(1 - X)}{K_r T_r^{bm-1} k_r^m M^{bm} \left(Y - \frac{x'_r}{M}\right)^{bm} - V_r - \frac{x'_r}{M}(V_p - V_r)} dx'_r}{\int_0^{D_p - x'_{c(p)}} \frac{1 - \frac{x'_p}{M}(1 - X)}{K_p T_p^{bm-1} k_p^m M^{bm} \left(1 - Y - \frac{x'_p}{M}\right)^{bm} + V_p - \frac{x'_p}{M}(V_p - V_r)} dx'_p}$$

Let $t_1 = \frac{x'_p}{M}$ and $t_2 = \frac{x'_r}{M}$, the limits of integration are modified accordingly after

this substitution:

$$\frac{H_r}{H_p} = \frac{\int_0^{Y - \frac{x'_{c(r)}}{M}} \frac{X + t_2(1 - X)}{K_r T_r^{bm-1} k_r^m M^{bm} (Y - t_2)^{bm} - V_r - t_2(V_p - V_r)} dt_2}{\int_0^{1 - Y - \frac{x'_{c(p)}}{M}} \frac{1 - t_1(1 - X)}{K_p T_p^{bm-1} k_p^m M^{bm} (1 - Y - t_1)^{bm} + V_p - t_1(V_p - V_r)} dt_1}$$

When $bm=1$, the above equation reduces to:

$$\frac{H_r}{H_p} = \frac{\int_0^{Y - \frac{x'_{c(r)}}{M}} \frac{t_2(1-X) + X}{t_2(-K_r k_r^m M - V_p + V_r) + K_r k_r^m M Y - V_r} dt_2}{\int_0^{1-Y - \frac{x'_{c(p)}}{M}} \frac{t_1(1-X) - 1}{t_1(K_p k_p^m M + V_p - V_r) - K_p k_p^m M(1-Y) - V_p} dt_1}$$

Assume that:

$$C_{r1} = -K_r k_r^m M - V_p + V_r$$

$$C_{r2} = K_r k_r^m M Y - V_r$$

$$C_{p1} = K_p k_p^m M + V_p - V_r$$

$$C_{p2} = -K_p k_p^m M(1-Y) - V_p$$

$$N_r = Y - \frac{x'_{c(r)}}{M}$$

$$N_p = 1 - Y - \frac{x'_{c(p)}}{M}$$

It follows that:

$$\frac{H_r}{H_p} = \frac{\int_0^{N_r} \frac{t_2(1-X) + X}{t_2 C_{r1} + C_{r2}} dt_2}{\int_0^{N_p} \frac{t_1(1-X) - 1}{t_1 C_{p1} + C_{p2}} dt_1}$$

Based on the integral formula for linear rational functions, the above equation can

be integrated into an analytical form:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{N_r(1-X)}{C_{r1}} + \frac{C_{r1}X - C_{r2}(1-X)}{C_{r1}^2} \ln \frac{C_{r1}N_r + C_{r2}}{C_{r2}} \\ &= \frac{H_r}{H_p} \left[\frac{N_p(1-X)}{C_{p1}} + \frac{-C_{p1} - C_{p2}(1-X)}{C_{p1}^2} \ln \frac{C_{p1}N_p + C_{p2}}{C_{p2}} \right] \end{aligned}$$

SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURES

Figure S1.

Interface of the interactive program developed in this study. The program is openly accessible on GitHub: <https://github.com/Zhou-Chao0630/SDD-V>.

Figure S2.

Numerical simulation results. (A) The numerical simulation result at $U_p = 1$ mm/yr,

$U_r = 0.2$ mm/yr, $V_p = 0$ mm/yr, $V_r = 0$ mm/yr. (B) The numerical simulation result at

$U_p = 1$ mm/yr, $U_r = 0.2$ mm/yr, $V_p = 1$ mm/yr, $V_r = 1$ mm/yr. (C) The numerical simulation result at $U_p = 1$ mm/yr, $U_r = 0.2$ mm/yr, $V_p = 2$ mm/yr, $V_r = 2$ mm/yr. (D) The numerical simulation result at $U_p = 1$ mm/yr, $U_r = 0.4$ mm/yr, $V_p = 0$ mm/yr, $V_r = 0$ mm/yr. (E) The numerical simulation result at $U_p = 1$ mm/yr, $U_r = 0.4$ mm/yr, $V_p = 1$ mm/yr, $V_r = 1$ mm/yr. (F) The numerical simulation result at $U_p = 1$ mm/yr, $U_r = 0.4$ mm/yr, $V_p = 2$ mm/yr, $V_r = 2$ mm/yr. (G) The numerical simulation result at $U_p = 1$ mm/yr, $U_r = 0.6$ mm/yr, $V_p = 0$ mm/yr, $V_r = 0$ mm/yr. (H) The numerical simulation result at $U_p = 1$ mm/yr, $U_r = 0.6$ mm/yr, $V_p = 1$ mm/yr, $V_r = 1$ mm/yr. (I) The numerical simulation result at $U_p = 1$ mm/yr, $U_r = 0.6$ mm/yr, $V_p = 2$ mm/yr, $V_r = 2$ mm/yr. (J) The numerical simulation result at $U_p = 1$ mm/yr, $U_r = 0.8$ mm/yr, $V_p = 0$ mm/yr, $V_r = 0$ mm/yr. (K) The numerical simulation result at $U_p = 1$ mm/yr, $U_r = 0.8$ mm/yr, $V_p = 1$ mm/yr, $V_r = 1$ mm/yr. (L) The numerical simulation result at $U_p = 1$ mm/yr, $U_r = 0.8$ mm/yr, $V_p = 2$ mm/yr, $V_r = 2$ mm/yr. (M) The numerical simulation result at $U_p = 0.8$ mm/yr, $U_r = 1$ mm/yr, $V_p = 0$ mm/yr, $V_r = 0$ mm/yr. (N) The numerical simulation result at $U_p = 0.8$ mm/yr, $U_r = 1$ mm/yr, $V_p = 1$ mm/yr, $V_r = 1$ mm/yr. (O) The numerical simulation result at $U_p = 0.8$ mm/yr, $U_r = 1$ mm/yr, $V_p = 2$ mm/yr, $V_r = 2$ mm/yr. (P) The numerical simulation result at $U_p = 0.6$ mm/yr, $U_r = 1$ mm/yr, $V_p = 0$ mm/yr, $V_r = 0$ mm/yr. (Q) The numerical simulation result at $U_p = 0.6$ mm/yr, $U_r = 1$ mm/yr, $V_p = 1$ mm/yr, $V_r = 1$ mm/yr. (R) The numerical simulation result at $U_p = 0.6$ mm/yr, $U_r = 1$ mm/yr, $V_p = 2$ mm/yr, $V_r = 2$ mm/yr. (S) The numerical simulation result at $U_p = 0.4$ mm/yr, $U_r = 1$ mm/yr, $V_p = 0$ mm/yr, $V_r = 0$ mm/yr. (T) The numerical simulation result at $U_p = 0.4$ mm/yr, $U_r = 1$ mm/yr, $V_p = 1$ mm/yr, $V_r = 1$ mm/yr. (U) The numerical simulation result at $U_p = 0.4$ mm/yr, $U_r = 1$ mm/yr, $V_p = 2$ mm/yr, $V_r = 2$ mm/yr. (V) The numerical simulation result at $U_p = 0.2$ mm/yr, $U_r = 1$ mm/yr, $V_p = 0$ mm/yr, $V_r = 0$ mm/yr. (W) The numerical simulation result at $U_p = 0.2$ mm/yr, $U_r = 1$ mm/yr, $V_p = 1$ mm/yr, $V_r = 1$ mm/yr. (X) The numerical simulation result at $U_p = 0.2$ mm/yr, $U_r = 1$ mm/yr, $V_p = 2$ mm/yr, $V_r = 2$ mm/yr. The black curve represents the steady-state position of the MDD. The maximum, minimum and average values of MDD positions are provided in Table S1.

Figure S3.

Characteristics of the river pair in the Min Shan region. **(A)** Long profiles of the river pair. The ratio of fluvial channel heights (H_r/H_p) yielded a value of 0.55, derived from the elevations of the base level and channel head. **(B)** Slope-area plot of the river pair. A critical area (A_c) of 2×10^6 m² was applied to exclude hillslope segments. The analysis was performed using the Topographic Analysis Kit and TopoToolbox in MATLAB.

Figure S4.

Curve fitting of Hack's coefficient (k) and exponent (b) in the Min Shan region. **(A)** Fitting results for the river on the western side of the Min Shan's MDD. **(B)** Fitting results for the river on the eastern side of the Min Shan's MDD.

SUPPLEMENTARY TABLE

Table S1. The maximum, minimum and average values of MDD positions in numerical simulations.

Numerical Model	U_p	U_r	V_p	V_r	D_r/M_{\max} (%)	D_r/M_{avg} (%)	D_r/M_{\min} (%)
Fig. 3A	1	0	0	0	77.74	71.975	66.21
Fig. S2A	1	0.2	0	0	71.32	66.585	61.85
Fig. S2D	1	0.4	0	0	67.8	62.38	56.96
Fig. S2G	1	0.6	0	0	62.35	57.32	52.29
Fig. S2J	1	0.8	0	0	60.29	54.75	49.21
Fig. 3B	1	1	0	0	57.07	49.965	42.86
Fig. S2M	0.8	1	0	0	48.93	44.87	40.81
Fig. S2P	0.6	1	0	0	48.93	42.85	36.77
Fig. S2S	0.4	1	0	0	40.88	37.125	33.37
Fig. S2V	0.2	1	0	0	36.32	31.16	26
Fig. 3C	0	1	0	0	29.47	23.98	18.49
Fig. 3D	1	0	1	1	73.94	68.895	63.85
Fig. S2B	1	0.2	1	1	70.62	63.605	56.59
Fig. S2E	1	0.4	1	1	62.01	54.84	47.67
Fig. S2H	1	0.6	1	1	52.93	45.595	38.26
Fig. S2K	1	0.8	1	1	54.79	45.86	36.93
Fig. 3E	1	1	1	1	47.98	41.71	35.44
Fig. S2N	0.8	1	1	1	43.95	36.615	29.28
Fig. S2Q	0.6	1	1	1	38.9	33.505	28.11
Fig. S2T	0.4	1	1	1	38.42	31.405	24.39
Fig. S2W	0.2	1	1	1	32.36	25.985	19.61
Fig. 3F	0	1	1	1	27.9	21.045	14.19
Fig. 3G	1	0	2	2	63.79	56.14	48.49
Fig. S2C	1	0.2	2	2	59.33	50.88	42.43
Fig. S2F	1	0.4	2	2	50.24	40.04	29.84
Fig. S2I	1	0.6	2	2	44.03	35.74	27.45
Fig. S2L	1	0.8	2	2	41.64	32.55	23.46
Fig. 3H	1	1	2	2	38.71	30.21	21.71
Fig. S2O	0.8	1	2	2	36.69	28.775	20.86
Fig. S2R	0.6	1	2	2	29.68	23.465	17.25
Fig. S2U	0.4	1	2	2	30	21.87	13.74
Fig. S2X	0.2	1	2	2	23.3	16.605	9.91
Fig. 3I	0	1	2	2	18.95	13.105	7.26

The “Numerical Model” column represents the image numbers corresponding to the numerical simulation results. The “ U_p , U_r , V_p and V_r ” columns represent the parameters employed in the numerical simulations. The “ D_r/M_{\max} , D_r/M_{avg} and

D_r/M_{\min} ” columns represent the maximum, average, and minimum values of the MDD positions, respectively.